

Microwave Irradiation In The Structural Elucidation Of Non-Conventional Seeds Gums Of Cassia Javanica

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Abstract

Cassia javanica is a tropical American climber naturalized in Southern Northern America. It is common throughout India in gardens and as a denizen. It is a slender glabrous twinned. Leaves 7.5-12.5 cm by 5-7.5cm, pinnate, segments numerous, linear, distant and peduncles few flowered. Corolla mid-sized, crimson or white sepals, which is elliptical. Corolla tube narrow, long and mouth rather small. Ovary completely four celled and four ovular. Capsule ovoid, smooth, 4 celled and seeds nearly glabrous. It has star shaped scarlet and pink or white blooms amid deep green deeply lobed leaves. It is a member of the morning glory family and is an annual.

People consider it to have cooling properties. The powered leaves are applied to bleeding piles, while a preparation of the juice with goat ghee is administered internally. Leaves are administered as a paste for carbuncles. Common name of *Cassia javanica* is **Red jasmine** in English and **Java ki Rani** in Hindi.

Keywords

Cassia Javanica, Microwave Irradiation, Conventional Method, Structural Elucidation.

Introduction

The seed gum from *Cassia javanica* is reported [1] to have a straight chain of β -D-(1 \rightarrow 4) linked D-mannopyranosyl units with galactopyranosyl units attached glycosidically on C-6 position of some of the mannose units by a α -linkages. The ratio of galactose to mannose in the seed gum has been previously reported [2] to be 1.00: 3.23.

For the structural elucidation, a polysaccharide is first hydrolyzed into the constituent monosaccharides under mildest conditions [3] possible so as to avoid any degradation of the monosaccharides during hydrolysis. Hydrolytic study for the polysaccharide is slow and quite time consuming but unavoidable technique, used invariably for the structural elucidation of any unknown polysaccharide. Acid hydrolysis of a seed gum requires either prolonged heating (>48h) with 2 NH_2SO_4 [4] or it takes 4h heating with 1 M trifluoroacetic acid. [5] Recently microwave irradiation have been shown to be very effective tool to completely hydrolyzed the seed gums into their component monosaccharides. [6]

Objective of study

In the present study the microwave promoted hydrolysis and methylation analysis of the *Cassia javanica* seed gum have been undertaken to find out whether the microwave method of hydrolysis and methylation, which has been recently used for Guar gum can be applied to the non-conventional seed galactomannans as well. No literature is available about the use of microwave irradiation in hydrolytic fragmentation and methylation analysis of the non-conventional galactomannans.

Review of Literature

The O-methylation technique is also of outstanding importance for the structural polysaccharide chemistry. [7] It is an exhaustive and laborious method and requires several hours to determine the position and types of linkages between the building block units of the polysaccharides. The method consists of the methylation of the polysaccharide; its hydrolysis to methylated sugars and the separation, identification and quantitative estimation of the components of the mixture. The methylation of the polysaccharide is usually carried out by Denhum and Woodhouse [8] and by Haworth method. [9] In general Haworth method

(repeated 3 to 4 times) gives partially methylated polysaccharide and the product has to be completely methylated further by Purdie & Irvine method with warm

methyl iodide in the presence of silver oxide. However, the Purdie methylation^[10] is not always very effective and generally has to be repeated many times. It has been also reported in literature to have a de-polymerization action. Hakomori method^[11] is more convenient using strong base methyl sulfinylmethylsodium and methyl iodide in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) but the polysaccharide is required to be soluble in DMSO. A more recent method involves dissolution of the polysaccharide in DMSO by sonication followed by treatment with NaOH and methyl iodide.^[12] Very recently microwave irradiation^[13] has been used for the successful methylation of the Guar gum where Guar gum could be methylated very easily using dimethylsulphate and aqueous solution of the sodium hydroxide solution in a very short time.

The fully methylated polysaccharide is hydrolyzed into its constituent methylated monosaccharides using –

1. Trifluoroacetic acid^[14] or
2. Methanolic hydrogen chloride^[15] or
3. 90-98% formic acid ^[16-17] followed by mineral acid

Result and Discussion

Isolation of the Seed Gums

The polysaccharides were isolated from the defatted and decolorized crushed seeds of *Cassia javanica* plant by extraction with cold 1.0% acetic acid followed by precipitation with 95% ethanol.

Purification

The polysaccharide was purified by –

1. Multiple precipitation
2. Deproteinization
3. Complexation with metal ions

1. Multiple precipitation or repeated precipitation

The crude dry polysaccharide was dissolved in 1% acetic acid and precipitated by adding the acid solutions slowly to excess of ethanol with continuous stirring. Dissolution and reprecipitation was repeated several times, to obtain the polysaccharide.

2. Deproteinization^[18]

The polysaccharide obtained after multiple precipitation was deproteinized by shaking their aqueous solution, with chloroform in a separating funnel. The denatured proteins formed a yellow brown gel at the water-chloroform interface that was separated. This process was repeated four times to remove almost all the proteins.

3. Complexation with Fehling's solution^[19]

The desiccated crude polysaccharide was dissolved in water and excess of Fehling's solution was added, after that the copper complex was precipitated. The complex was centrifuged and thoroughly washed with dilute Fehling's solution to remove the adsorbed unreacted polysaccharide. The complex was then suspended separately in cold water and was decomposed by 1.0 N HCl. The polysaccharide was reprecipitated by adding slowly the above solution to a large excess of ethanol with stirring. Dissolution and reprecipitation was repeated to obtain polysaccharide, which was dried in vacuum oven over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The desiccated polysaccharide was white amorphous non-reducing material, which was easily dispersed in water forming viscous, mucilaginous solution at room temperature. It showed the minimum ash content 0.31% and optical rotation $[\alpha]^{25}_D + 51.4^0(\text{water})$. It was found to be free from nitrogen, sulphur and halogens. The methoxyl, uronide and acetyl groups were negligible.

Homogeneity

The purified polysaccharide was checked for its homogeneity by the following technique-

1. Fractional precipitation
2. Zone electrophoresis
3. Acetylation followed by deacetylation
4. Paper chromatographic examinations in different solvent systems

(i) Fractional precipitation

The polysaccharide was dissolved in water and precipitated in two fractions by adding different volumes of ethanol each time. Both the samples were analyzed quantitatively by the method of Hirst and Jones.^[20] The results of the analysis were identical to the original polysaccharide showing the polysaccharide to be homogeneous.

(ii) Zone electrophoresis

A portion of the polysaccharide was subjected to conventional zone electrophoresis on Whatman No.42 1MM chromatography paper in Borate buffer (pH 9.3). The chromatograms were cut into thirty segments each 1 cm wide, which were numbered consecutively from the anodic end and down to the cathodic end. Each segment was eluted with phenol-sulphuric acid reagent. The intensity of the characteristics yellow orange color developed in aqueous eluate of each segment was measured in a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using filter No. 50. A plot of absorbance against segment number showed only a single sharp peak showing the polysaccharide to be homogeneous.

(iii) Acetylation followed by deacetylation

The polysaccharide was acetylated with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate by the usual method. Acetylated product showed $[\alpha]^{28}_D + 19^0$ (Chloroform). A portion of the acetyl derivative on deacetylation showed the same optical activity, $[\alpha]^{28}_D + 52.1^0$ (Water), as the original polysaccharide showing the homogeneous character of the polysaccharide.

(iv) Paper chromatographic examinations in different solvent systems

The polysaccharide was hydrolyzed with 2 N sulphuric acid, neutralized, filtered and concentrated the filtrate under reduced pressure to syrup. The hydrolysate was examined in three solvent systems (A), (C) and (H). In all three solvent systems, the results were identical showing the homogeneous character of the polysaccharide.

Hydrolytic study of the polysaccharide

The polysaccharide was completely hydrolyzed with 0.2 N sulphuric acid under 100% MW power in 170 seconds, while using conventional method complete hydrolysis could be achieved with 2.0 N sulphuric acid under reflux condition in 48h. Paper chromatographic analysis detected the presence of monosaccharides-

1. D- galactose (structure – 1)
2. D- mannose (structure – 2)

The identities of the sugars were confirmed by specific rotation, preparation of their crystalline derivatives and co-chromatography with authentic samples.

D-galactose

D-mannose

Quantitative estimation of the monosaccharides in the microwave hydrolyzed hydrolysate of the *Cassia javanica* seed gum by periodate oxidation^[20] taking D-ribose as reference sugars showed that galactose and mannose are present in 1:3.25 molar ratio in the polysaccharide that was very close to the reported value as obtained by the conventional method.^[2]

Graded hydrolysis of the polysaccharide with 0.005 N sulphuric acid under 100% MW power and the paper chromatographic separation of the hydrolyzed at the various intervals indicated that galactose was released first and mannose was detected only after 25 seconds showing that the galactose units are present at the periphery of the polysaccharide bonded with weaker glycosidic linkages, most probably α - linkages as also revealed conventionally.

To determine the position of linkages between building units of the polysaccharide, it was methylated using methyl iodide in aqueous 30% KOH under 100% MW power in 330 seconds. The fully methylated product was a semi solid, brown glassy mass had $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 28.6^0$ (Chloroform) and was devoid of an absorption band in the hydroxyl region of its IR spectrum.

Complete hydrolysate of the methylated polysaccharide obtained using microwave irradiation on paper chromatographic analysis in the solvent (A) revealed the presence of three methylated sugars, same as reported by the conventional studies-

1. 2,3,4,6- tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose (Structure – 3)
2. 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose (Structure – 4)
3. 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-mannose (Structure – 5)

2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D-galactose (i) was recrystallized from petroleum ether, had R_{TMG} 0.86 in solvent (A), mp 71-72 0C and $[\alpha]_D^{32} - 120^0$ (Water). On treatment with ethanolic aniline gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, mp 190-191 0C . This sequence of evidences clearly proved it to be 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose.

2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose (ii) was obtained as Syrup, R_{TMG} in solvent (A) 0.55, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.80^0$ (Water), lit.^[22] for 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16^0$ (Water).

1,4,6-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, mp 191-192 0C , $[\alpha]_D^{26} + 63.9^0$ (Chloroform), lit. 1,4,6-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, m.p. 194 0C , $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 65^0$ (Chloroform). Which showed that methylated sugar (ii) was 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose.

2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D-galactose
Structure -3

2, 3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose
Structure -4

2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose
Structure - 5

2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose(iii) was also isolated in the form of Syrup, R_{TMG} in solvent (A) 0.81, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 10.4^0$ (water), lit^[23] for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 10^0$ (water).

The syrup (80 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (6 ml) and p-nitrobenzoyl chloride (100 mg) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 45 minutes at 60-70 °C and left overnight at room temperature. A saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate was added drop wise until no effervescence occurred. After adding water (10 ml), the product was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform was then taken off in vacuum and the residue was recrystallized from petroleum ether. The derivative 1,4-bis-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose had m.p. 168-188 °C and $[\alpha]_D^{26} +32^0$ (Chloroform).^[24]

The syrup was oxidized with bromine water and the product was crystallized from acetone, m.p. 89-82 °C, lit.^[25] for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-γ-(+)-mannolactone 80-83 °C.

The lactone was boiled under reflux in alcohol with phenyl hydrazine (45 mg). It was then refluxed with a little amount of animal charcoal in ethanol and filtered. On cooling a crystalline product was obtained, which was recrystallized from ethanol. m.p. 128-130 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 19^0$ (water) lit.^[26] for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannoic acid phenyl hydrazine, m.p. 129-130 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 20^0$ (water).

The above results indicated that methylated sugar (iii) was 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose.

The quantitative estimation of methylated monosaccharides in the hydrolysate obtained by hydrolysis of fully methylated *Cassia javanica* seed gum (obtained by microwave method) by alkaline hypo iodite ^[27] method using D-glucose as reference sugar. The results showed that 2,3,4,6-tetramethyl-D-galactose, 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose and 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose were present in the molecular ratio of 1.00:1.07:2.19 that is very close to reported ratio as obtained by conventional studies.^[2]

The results from methylation analysis showed that the microwave method of methylation can be generalized and can be used not only for the guar gum but also for the other non-conventional seed galactomannans like *Cassia javanica*.

To determine the anomeric configuration of the glycosidic linkages, the character of branching and the sequence sugar units, polysaccharides are subjected to conventionally partially hydrolyzed with 0.1 N sulphuric acid in 10-12 h. But in microwave method *Cassia javanica* seed gum was partially hydrolyzed with 0.05 N sulphuric acid under 100% MW power in 45 seconds. The hydrolyzate upon paper chromatographic separation on preparative scale afforded 3 oligosaccharides along with D- galactose and D-mannose same as reported to be obtained by conventional methods.

The following oligosaccharides were identified and characterized-

- (i) Epimelibiose: α-D-galactopyranosyl-(1 →6)-D-mannopyranose.
- (ii) Mannobiose: β-D-mannopyranosyl-(1 →4)-D- mannopyranose.
- (iii) Galactosylmannobiose: α-D-galactopyranosyl-(1 →6)-β-D-mannopyranosyl-(1 →4)-D-mannopyranose.

Epimelibiose (Structure-6) – A crystalline solid reducing sugar. On complete hydrolysis gave galactose and mannose in equimolar ratio.

Mannobiose (Structure-7) – A crystalline reducing sugar.

Galactosylmannobiose (Structure-8) – Complete hydrolysis of the sugar gave galactose and mannose.

Formation of these oligosaccharides supports the finding previously derived from the methylation studies.

KingDraw

Epimelibiose
 (Structure -6)

KingDraw

Mannobiose
 Structure - 7

KingDraw

GalactosylMannobiose
 Structure - 8

On the basis of the results obtained so far, particularly from complete, graded and partial hydrolysis, methylation studies of *Cassia javanica* seed gum following valuable information have been derived:

1. Polysaccharide can be completely and partially hydrolyzed using microwave irradiation.
2. For hydrolysis and methylation studies by microwave method, milder reagents are required in comparison to the conventional methods.
3. In microwave method significantly, less time is required than the conventional method.
4. Results from the microwave and conventional methods are in close agreement for the *Cassia javanica* seed gum as reported for the commercial guar gum.
5. Thus, microwave promoted method of the hydrolysis and methylation can be applied to the non- conventional galactomannans from *Cassia* species too as has been recently used for the Guar gum and such procedures may be generalized.

Experimental Method

A Kenstar (Model no. MOW 9811, 1200W) domestic microwave oven was used for all the experiments. All concentrations were carried out under diminished pressure at 35-40⁰C unless specified otherwise. Melting points are uncorrected and all specific rotations were measured at equilibrium. All residues were dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. Paper chromatography was conducted on Whatman No.42 1MM and 3MM papers at room temperature by descending technique using the following solvent mixtures:

- (A) 1- Butanol-ethanol- water (5:1:4)^[28]
 (B) 1-Butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5)^[29]
 (C) 1-Butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3)^[30]
 (D) Benzene-ethanol-water (169:47:15)^[31]
 (E) Butanone-water (1.0:1)^[32]
 (F) Ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (5:2:7)^[33]
 (G) Ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (2:1:2)^[34]
 (H) Ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (10:4:3)^[35]
 (I) 1-Butanol-ethanol-water (4:1:5)^[36]
 (J) Ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (9:2:2)^[37]
 (K) 1-Butanol-ethanol-ammonia-water (40:10:1:49)^[38]

Compositions are v/v, were the solvent mixture formed two phases, the water immiscible phase was used.

The spots were located by spraying chromatogram with aniline hydrogen phthalate,^[39] aniline oxalic acid^[40] or by naphthoresorcinol sulphuric acid^[41] and heating them at 100-122⁰C for 15-20 minutes in an electric oven.

Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded on a Brucker Victor-22 Infrared spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. Seeds were supplied by Himani Seed stores, Dehradun and identified by Department of Botany, Dayanand Vedic College, Orai, India.

Crushed seeds were preferred, instead of seed flour, as the starting material for the isolation of the polysaccharide.

Isolation of seed gums

The dried and crushed seeds (1.5 kg) of the plant were extracted successively and exhaustively with petroleum ether (60-80⁰C) and ethanol to remove oils, fats and other coloring material soluble in these solvents. The extracted seeds were dried and separately soaked in cold 1% aqueous acetic acid. The mixture was stirred mechanically for 9-10 hours and all were kept overnight to extract the mucilage as much as possible and squeezed them out through muslin clothe. This process was repeated many times till practically no precipitate was obtained by the addition of the extracts to an excess of ethanol. The combined extracts were filtered thrice through a thick cotton pad placed over a cloth in a Buckner funnel to remove the suspended fine particles. A heavy opaque viscous, mucilaginous solution was obtained from the plant seeds. The mucilage solutions obtained were added slowly to a large excess of 95% ethanol with constant stirring when a white

fibrous precipitate of the crude polysaccharide was obtained. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and then vigorously stirred in absolute alcohol, filtered and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride at room temperature.

Purification

The crude polysaccharide was purified by the following methods: -

- A. Multiple precipitation
- B. Deproteinization
- C. Complexation with Fehling's solution

A. Multiple precipitation

The dried crude polysaccharide was dissolved in distilled water (1.0 liters) containing 1% acetic acid with constant stirring. The solution was filtered and was added very slowly in a thin stream to ethanol (5 liters) with continuous vigorous stirring and kept overnight. All the precipitated polysaccharide was filtered washed with ethanol followed by absolute alcohol and dried. Dissolution and reprecipitation were repeated four times for getting white fibrous polysaccharide.

B. Deproteinization

The polysaccharide obtained after repeated precipitation was dissolved in water as above and the aqueous solution was shaken well with chloroform in a separating funnel, when the denatured proteins formed gel at the water chloroform interface. The mucilage layer was separated and the method was repeated six times to get rid of the proteins. The mucilage was regenerated by adding the aqueous layer to the large excess of ethanol with stirring.

C. Complexation with Fehling's solution

Excess of Fehling's solution was added to the aqueous solution of the deproteinized polysaccharide, consequently copper complex was precipitated.

The complex was centrifuged and treated with dilute Fehling's solution to remove the absorbed unreacted polysaccharide. The complex was then suspended in cold water and was decomposed by gradual addition of 1.0N hydrochloric acid with stirring till whole of the residue was dissolved. The solution was passed through a folded muslin cloth and the polysaccharide was regenerated by adding its solution slowly to ethanol (8 liters) with continuous stirring. This was filtered, dried and redissolved in 1% acetic acid and was reprecipitated as described above to get white fibrous polysaccharide.

Ash Content

The purified polysaccharide (200 mg) was incinerated in a silica crucible. After incineration, the crucible was cooled in a desiccator and weighed. From the weight of the residue (0.62 mg) the percentage of the ash content was found to be 0.31%.

Preliminary studies

The purified polysaccharide was a white amorphous material, light in weight and hydrated slowly to form viscous solution at room temperature. On the basis of quantitative results, methoxyl,^[42] acetyl^[43] and uronide^[44] contents were found to be negligible in the seed gum. Further quantitative tests for seed gum showed the absence of nitrogen, sulphur and halogen. The polysaccharide upon treatment with Fehling's solution formed insoluble copper complex but did not reduce them, showing the absence of free reducing sugars.

Examination of free sugars

The polysaccharide was examined for free sugars by applying three spots of their solution in water, on the strip of Whatman No.42 1MM chromatography paper (15 cm × 45 cm). The papers were developed in solvent 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3) for 40 hours separately, dried and cut lengthwise into three strips each containing one spot. The three strips were sprayed with three different reagents using naphthoresorcinol and trichloroacetic acid (give color with ketoses only) on one, aniline hydrogen phthalate on the second and silver nitrate in acetone followed by ethanolic sodium hydroxide on the third. The two papers were dried in an oven at 120⁰C and the third was air-dried. None of the strips showed any spot; hence the polysaccharide does not contain any free sugars.

Homogeneity of the Polysaccharide

The homogeneity of the polysaccharide was tested by the following methods:-

1. Fractional precipitation

2. Zone electrophoresis
3. Acetylation followed by deacetylation
4. Paper chromatographic examinations in different solvent systems

I. Fractional precipitation

The purified polysaccharide (3 gm) was suspended in distilled water (400 ml), stirred mechanically for nearly 8 hours and then 400ml of 90% ethanol added to it with stirring. The precipitated polysaccharide was filtered washed with ethanol followed by the ether and dried in vacuum desiccator, over anhydrous calcium chloride (fraction-A). The filtrate was again treated with another 600ml of 90% ethanol and when the polysaccharide precipitated, it was collected, washed and dried as above (fraction-B).

Both fractions were separately hydrolyzed with 2 N sulphuric acid.

Paper chromatographic analysis of the hydrolyzate of the (fraction A and B) gave galactose and mannose in molar ratio of 1:3.25 and the both the fraction retained the original specific rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 51.4^0$ (Water) indicating the homogenous character of polysaccharide.

II. Zone Electrophoresis

A strip support (15 cm × 45 cm) of Whatman No.42 1MM filter paper was marked with a pencil at 10 cm from one end (Anode) to indicate the starting line. 50 ml of the 0.3% solution of the polysaccharide in distilled water was placed in the starting line as a thin band not greater than 5 cm in length and as narrow as possible. After drying at room temperature, the strip was spread with borate buffer (0.2 N sodium decahydrate, pH 9.3) and suspended horizontally in the tank of an electrophoretic apparatus of which of two electrode compartments were holding approximately 800 ml of borate buffer (pH 9.3). After electrophoresis at 360 volt and 12.5mA for 6.5 hours, the strip support was removed and air dried. It was cut length wise into 5 cm strip and then each strip was further cut into 1cm segments, which were numbered consequently from the anode end down the strip to the cathode end. Material in each segment was eluted with 6ml of water for 30 minutes at room temperature. The extract was filtered through a plug of glass wool to remove cellulose fibers; 5ml of the filtrate was placed on the hard glass boiling tube (25 mm × 200mm) with 1 ml of 8.5% aqueous phenol. Then 15 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added rapidly, the stream of the acid being directed against the liquid surface in the center rather than against the side of the boiling tube in order to get good mixing event heat distribution. The tubes were allowed to stand for 10 minutes and then they were shaken, placed for 10-20 minutes in a water bath at 25-30⁰C and finally allowed to cool at room temperature. The absorbance of the yellow orange color was measured in a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using filter paper No. 50. Readings of 5 ml portion of the solutions were recorded. A blank was also run under identical conditions but without the polysaccharide. The color reaction with phenol sulphuric acid and measurement of the absorbance was carried out as already described. The corrected Klett readings were obtained by subtracting the blank readings from the corresponding segment of paper chromatogram containing the polysaccharide. The reading thus obtained was plotted against segment no. which showed only one peak indicating homogeneity of the polysaccharide.

The absorbance of blanks and extracts were measure against blank prepared by adding 1ml of 8.5% aqueous phenol to 5ml distilled water followed by 15ml of conc. sulphuric acid under the conditions described earlier.

The amount of the polysaccharide by using the expression-

$$m = \frac{31.74 \times \text{absorbance}}{0.20}$$

Table 1

Segment No.	Klett reading of elute	Klett reading of bank	Corrected Klett reading	Absorbance (A)	Amount of polysaccharide recovered in extract
1.	26	24	2.0	0.004	
2.	24	22	2.0	0.004	
3.	22	20	2.0	0.004	
4.	21	19	2.0	0.004	
5.	21	21	0.0	0.000	
6.	28	25	3.0	0.006	
7.	26	24	2.0	0.004	
8.	28	26	2.0	0.004	
9.	26	24	2.0	0.004	
10.	30	29	1.0	0.002	
11.	29	27	2.0	0.004	
12.	27	25	2.0	0.004	
13.	30	27	3.0	0.006	
14.	29	26	3.0	0.006	
15.	41	22	19.0	0.038	5.91
16.	61	21	40.0	0.080	12.50
17.	42	23	19.0	0.038	5.91
18.	21	19	2.0	0.004	
19.	23	21	2.0	0.004	
20.	26	23	3.0	0.006	
21.	22	22	0.0	0.000	
22.	21	21	0.0	0.000	
23.	20	19	1.0	0.000	
24.	19	17	2.0	0.004	
25.	19	19	0.0	0.000	
26.	21	19	2.0	0.004	
27.	21	20	1.0	0.002	
28.	20	18	2.0	0.004	
29.	10	8.0	2.0	0.004	
30.	12	10	2.0	0.004	

Where 'm' is expressed in micrograms (μ) per ml of the polysaccharide solution or extract.

Absorbance was measured on 5ml portion of the colored solution.

(a) Absorbance = $\frac{2 \times \text{Klett readings}}{100}$

100

(b) Amount of the polysaccharide was not calculated if the absorbance was below 0.01.

Complete hydrolysis of seed gum and identification of component sugars

2.00gm of the seed gum was dissolved in 150ml of 0.2 N sulphuric acid and out of it 20 ml of the gum solutions were exposed to 100% microwave power (2450 MHz) for different exposure time. Appropriate exposure time to get optimal results for the complete and partial hydrolysis of the seed gum was guessed by detecting the reducing property of the hydrolyzates by Fehling's solution during the hydrolysis and by paper chromatography. The results are summarized in the **Table-2**. Paper chromatography [solvent-1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3) and 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4)] of the complete hydrolyzate of the seed gum revealed the presence of galactose and mannose (as revealed by their Rf values). Results are summarized in **Table 3(a) and 3(b)**.

Table-2: Acid hydrolysis of seed gums with 0.2 N H₂SO₄ under MW irradiation

Seed gum	Time in minutes	Oligosaccharides Detected	Monosaccharides Detected
<i>Cassia javanica</i>	45 sec.	Epimelibiose, Mannobiose, Galactosylmannobiose	Traces of Galactose and Mannose
	170 sec.	Nil	Galactose and Mannose

Table 3: Monosaccharides identified by paper chromatography

Sugars identified	Rf 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3)	
	Found	Reported
D-Galactose	0.15	0.16
D- mannose	0.21	0.22

3(a)

Sugars identified	Rf 1-butano-etalanol-water (5:1:4)	
	Found	Reported
D- galactose	0.08	0.07
D- mannose	0.11	0.10

3(b)

A portion from hydrolyzate obtained by the hydrolysis using MW were dissolved in aqueous methanol and adsorbed on the cellulose column separately and separation of the constituent sugars was done using 1- butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4) as a solvent. Identities and configuration of the monosaccharides were confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic samples of galactose and mannose and preparation of their derivatives in each case.

To ensure the stability of the constituent monosaccharides under the microwave conditions, a control experiment was performed in which a known mixture of the galactose and the mannose in 20 ml of water was estimated gravimetrically by treating with excess of Fehling's solution and then filtering off, followed by washing with water and alcohol and weighing the amount of Cu_2O , before and after exposure under full microwave power for a definite exposure time. To ensure that hydrolyses of the seed gums to monosaccharides were complete under microwave conditions; galactose and mannose were estimated gravimetrically, in the complete hydrolyzate obtained conventionally (with 2 N H_2SO_4 for 48 h) as well as by microwaves (with 0.2 N H_2SO_4 under 100% MW power) both.

(a) Paper Chromatography

The paper chromatography of the hydrlyzates obtained from all the seed gums were performed as under-

The spots of hydrolyzate from the complete hydrolysis (MW) were applied on two sheets (10 cm × 45 cm) of Whatman no.42 1MM chromatography paper. The papers were developed in solvent 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4) and 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3) by descending unidimensional technique. The chromatograms were dried and sprayed with aniline hydrogen phthalate. Two spots were observed on heating the chromatograms at 120⁰C in an oven.

The Rf values of two spots correspond to D- galactose and D- mannose in the *cassia javanica* seed gum as shown in **Table-3(a) and 3(b)**.

For the seed gum, the identity of the sugars obtained from complete acid hydrolysis (MW and conventional method) was finally confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic samples D-galactose and D-mannose. The chromatograms were developed in aforesaid solvents.

(b) Column Chromatography

A portion from the hydrolyzate obtained from the complete hydrolysis of the seed gum under MW irradiations as well as by conventional hydrolysis separately, were dissolved in aqueous methanol (1:1) and the solutions were adsorbed over a cellulose column (2 cm × 37 cm). Overnight separations were affected with solvent 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3). Fractions of the elutes were collected in the usual way in each case and examined by paper co-chromatography with authentic samples of D-galactose and D- mannose in solvent 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11:6:3). The fractions containing same sugars were combined together, concentrated and recrystallized. Thus, the two fractions (1) and (2) was obtained and examined (**TABLE-4**).

(i) D- Galactose: -A reducing sugar.

(ii) D- Mannose: - A reducing sugar.

Table-4

Components	Melting point		Optical rotation	
	Found	Lit value	Found	Lit value
D-mannose-derivative	129	131	+12.57	+12.6
1. D-mannose-p-N-glycosyl amino benzoic acid	180	182		
2.Mannose phenyl hydrazone	199	199-200		
D-galactose-derivative	165	166	+79.21	+79
1.D-galactose phenyl hydrazone	154	155		
2.N-p-nitrophenyl-D-galactosyl amine	219	219		

Partial hydrolysis of the seed gum and identification of oligosaccharides

The oligosaccharides present in the partial hydrolyzate (MW hydrolyzed)

of the seed gum were detected by paper co-chromatography in solvent ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (2:1:2& 10:4:3) with the authentic sample's galactose, mannose and glucose; by comparing R_{gal} , R_{man} , R_{glu} , values of different oligosaccharides with the reference values. The partial hydrolyzate of the seed gum by conventional partial acid hydrolysis (with 0.1 N H_2SO_4 for 12 h on a water bath) and by the MW hydrolysis using 0.05 N H_2SO_4 gave identical oligosaccharides. Oligosaccharides were separated by hydrolyzing the seed gum (4 g) with MW method and the conventional method and hydrolyzates thus obtained were subjected to preparative paper chromatography on 3 MM in solvent 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11: 6: 3) followed by elution of the sugars with distilled water. These oligosaccharides were characterized by their m.p., optical rotation, etc. The seed gum produced same oligosaccharides on MW hydrolysis as are reported for the conventional partial hydrolysis.

A portion from the hydrolyzates obtained from partial hydrolysis under MW irradiation was dissolved in aqueous methanol (1:1) and the solution was absorbed over a cellulose column (2 X 37 cm) and subsequently overnight separations were affected with solvent 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5: 1: 4). Epimelibiose, Mannobiose and Galactosylmannobiose along with component sugars were detected in the seed gum, these were concentrated recrystallized and were characterized by their m.p. and optical rotations. (TABLE-5)

(i) **Epimelibiose**:- A crystalline reducing sugar.

(ii) **Mannobiose**:- A crystalline reducing sugar.

(iii) **Galactosylmannobiose**:- complete hydrolysis of the sugar gave galactose and mannose.

Table-5

SUGAR	M.P.($^{\circ}C$)		OPTICAL ROTATION $[a]_D^{32}$ (WATER)	
	Found	Lit Value	Found	Lit Value
Epimelibiose	198	199-200	+119.9	+120
Mannobiose	200	201-203	-7.51	-7.50
Galactosylmannobiose	227	227	+92.90	+93

Quantitative examination of component sugars:-

The component sugars of the polysaccharides were quantified by the method of Hirst and Jones. The result of the quantitative estimation of component monosaccharides of the seed gum are summarized in Table-6

The polysaccharide (300 mg) was hydrolyzed with 0.2 N sulphuric acid under MW irradiation for complete hydrolysis (Table-2). Hydrolyzate obtained was cooled at room temperature and to each of them 60 ml of distilled water and 30 mg of D-ribose were added. The solutions were neutralized with barium carbonate, filtered and the filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure to about 5 ml. For quantitative estimation, chromatography papers were run for the hydrolyzate and component sugars were estimated separately by periodate method as described below-

Sheet of Whatman No. 42 3 MM chromatographic paper (30 cm X 45 cm) was used. Three guide strips (5 cm) two on either edge and one in the center were marked on each paper. A portion of the concentrated hydrolyzate was placed along the starting line (8 cm away from the upper edge) in the form of thin compact bands. A guide spot of the hydrolyzate was placed in center of each guide strip on the starting line. The three chromatograms along with the three

control papers were developed in solvent 1-butanol-2-propanol-water (11: 6: 3) for 46 hours. After drying the chromatograms, the guide strips were cut lengthwise, sprayed with aniline hydrogen phthalate (A.H.P.) and heated in an oven at 120 °C, for 15-20 minutes to locate the positions of the sugars. With the help of these guide strips the appropriate sections were cut from the unsprayed portion of each chromatogram containing the component sugars. Similarly, the sections from control chromatograms were also cut. Each section containing the sugar and the corresponding control was cut into small pieces and extracted separately with 10 ml of distilled water. Each eluate was then oxidized with 10 ml of 0.25 M sodium metaperiodate solution. The liberated formic acid (in 2 ml of the oxidized eluate) was titrated with standard alkali, after destroying excess of oxidant with ethylene glycol (2 ml), using methyl red as indicator. Control readings were subtracted to get the actual titer values. From MW hydrolyzate the ratio of galactose to mannose in *Cassia javanica* was found to be 1.00: 3.25; which are closer to the reported results by conventional hydrolytic methods i.e. 1.00: 3.23.

Table-6: Quantitative estimation of the monosaccharides in the MW hydrolyzate

Seed Gum	Sugar	Volume Of Alkali Used In ml			Corresponding Amount Of Sugar In mg		
		A	B	C	A	B	C
Cassia javanica	D-galactose	1.12	1.12	1.10	0.39513	0.39513	0.38808
	D-mannose	3.58	3.58	3.52	1.27269	1.27269	1.24185
	D-ribose	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.0918	0.0918	0.0918

Methylation Analysis:

(a) Methylation of the *Cassia javanica* seed gum under microwave irradiation:

The pure seed gum (1.0 gm) was dissolved in 25 ml 10% aqueous KOH, stirring vigorously on a magnetic stirrer. 40 ml of 30% aqueous KOH and 20 ml of methyl iodide were added to the above solution in three equal installments and exposed at full MW power after each addition. The *Cassia javanica* seed gum was completely methylated in 330 seconds. On the addition of each installment of the reagents, the pH of the reaction mixture was observed to be 12, which decreases to 2.5 after the first exposure, 7-8 after the second exposure and 12 were observed after the third exposure which in turn indicated the completion of the reaction. The reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl₃ thoroughly, the extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The methylated product was obtained as a crispy light-yellow product, yield 790 mg, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +28.6^0$ (Chloroform). Methylated gum showed no absorption peaks at the hydroxyl regions. (Fig-1)

(b) Hydrolysis of fully methylated seed gum:

300 mg of the methylated seed gum was dissolved in 20 ml 60% aqueous HCOOH and the solution was exposed to 100% MW power for 90 seconds. The solution was then concentrated and the last traces of formic acid were removed under vacuum. It was then dissolved in 15 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ and exposed to full MW power for 105 seconds. The hydrolyzate was cooled, neutralized with barium carbonate, filter and concentrated under the reduced pressure to light yellow syrup.

(a) Paper chromatography

The methylated sugars were separated on Whatman no. 42 1MM paper using solvent mixture 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4). The chromatogram showed three spots after spraying with aniline hydrogen phthalate and drying at 120°C. The R_{TMG} values were calculated in each case and compared with those reported in literature as given in Table-7.

Table-7

S. no.	Methylated sugars identified	Solvent 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4)		Solvent 1-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5)	
		R _{TMG} Found	R _{TMG} Reported	R _{TMG} Found	R _{TMG} Reported
1.	2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D- galactose	0.87	0.88	0.93	0.93
2.	2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose	0.54	0.54	0.60	0.62
3.	2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose	0.80	0.81	0.83	0.84

(b) Column chromatography:

A portion of the hydrolyzate of the methylated *Cassia javanica* seed gum was dissolved in aqueous methanol (1:1) and the solution was absorbed over a cellulose column (2 cm × 37 cm) and overnight separation was affected with solvent 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4). Fractions of the elutes were collected in the usual way and examined by paper chromatography with authentic sample.

The fractions containing following methylated monosaccharides and were identified by their m.p., optical rotation and by forming their crystalline derivatives.

(i) 2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D-galactose

Solid R_{TMG} in solvent 1-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4) 0.87, M.P. 70-71 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 117$ to $+ 122^0$ (water), M.P. 71-72 °C. It gave red color with p-anisidine hydrochloride and brownish red color with aniline hydrogen phthalate.

The methylated sugar (80mg) was refluxed on water bath for 4h with aniline (40 ml) in alcohol and 2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosyl amine was obtained, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 77.7^0$ (Acetone).

(ii) 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose

Syrup, R_{TMG} in solvent (A) 0.55, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.80^0$ (water), lit. for 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16^0$ (water).

1,4,6-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose, m.p. 191-192 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{26} + 63.9^0$ (Chloroform), lit. 1,4,6-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose, m.p. 194°C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 65^0$ (Chloroform). Which showed that methylated sugar (ii) was 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose (**structure-4**).

(iii) 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose

Syrup R_{TMG} in solvent (A) 0.81, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 10^0$ (water), lit. for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 10^0$ (water).

The syrup (80 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (6 ml) and p-nitrobenzoyl chloride (100 mg) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 45 minutes at 60-70 °C and left overnight at room temperature. A saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate was added drop wise until no effervescence occurred. After adding water (10 ml), the product was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform was then taken off in vacuum and the residue was recrystallized from petroleum ether. The derivative 1,4-bis-p-nitrobenzoate of 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose had m.p. 168-188 °C and $[\alpha]_D^{26} + 32^0$ (Chloroform).

The syrup was oxidized with bromine water and the product was crystallized from acetone, m.p. 80-82 °C, lit. for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-γ-(+)-mannolactone 82-83 °C.

The lactone was boiled under reflux in alcohol with phenyl hydrazine (45 mg). It was then refluxed with a little amount of animal charcoal in ethanol and filtered. On cooling a crystalline product was obtained, which was recrystallized from ethanol. M.P. 128-130 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 19^0$ (water) lit. for 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannoic acid phenyl hydrazide, M.P. 129-130 °C, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 20^0$ (water).

The above results indicated that methylated sugar (iii) was 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose. (**structure-5**)

Quantitative estimation of methylated components:

The methylated sugars were estimated by alkaline hypiodite method. Iodine solution (0.1 N, 2 ml) was added to the sugars elutes contained in 50 ml conical flasks provided with a ground glass joint stopper. A solution (2 ml) containing 0.2 M sodium carbonate and 0.2 M sodium bicarbonate was then added to each flask and the flasks were stoppered. The corresponding control experiment was also carried on 10 ml of water. After 4 hours the reaction mixture was acidified with 2N sulphuric acid and then 2 ml of 15% potassium iodide solution was added to it.

The liberated iodine was titrated against 0.01N sodium thiosulphate solution using as indicator. The results are given in the following **Table-8**.

Table-8

Sr. no.	Name of methylated sugars	Volume of hypo used (ml)			Corresponding amount of sugar (mg)		
		A	B	C	A	B	C
1.	2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D-galactose	0.52	0.52	0.44	0.5568	0.5568	0.4796
2.	2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose	0.56	0.60	0.60	0.5320	0.5320	0.4560
3.	2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose	1.14	1.14	0.98	1.1628	1.1628	0.9588
4.	D-glucose	0.26	0.26	0.22	0.234	0.2340	0.198

Normality of hypo = 0.01 N

Conclusion

The above result corresponds to an average molar ratio between 2,3,4,6-tetra-o-methyl-D-galactose; 2,3-di-o-methyl-D-mannose; and 2,3,6-tri-o-methyl-D-mannose as 1.00:1.07:2.19, closer to the reported values found by conventional method.

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